

The Acharya as We saw Him*

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I deem it a great privilege and honour, that our Society has asked me to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture this year.

When I joined Science College, thirty five years ago, Sir P. C. Ray was the then Palit Professor of Chemistry—a venerable old man, with a frail body but spirited looks, altogether giving the impression of a sage or a crank depending on the taste of the onlooker. But to the informed he was a great man, loved, admired and respected. Like all great men he had his idiosyncrasies; one of these was that to bring home a point, he would catch a hapless student with a frontal vice-like grip and go on pounding him hard on the chest until some how he would squeeze out to remain ever a chastised respecter from a distance; I wonder what would have happened had the students in question been the usual weakling of the 'ration' generation.

To the nation he was a wise leader and a capable servant, but to the student body, to us all, he was a unique source of inspiration. At that time Acharya was long past the prime of his scientific eminence but somehow he appeared to us to be a towering personality in science, a kind of Scientist-Sannyashi whose mere blessing would make the budding scientists in us bloom into scientists of great stature. The then student body accustomed to be surrounded by thick patches of callous indifference and outright incompetence, intuitively found in Sir P. C. Ray, a great teacher, chemist, leader and patriot combined into one. It is impossible for the present generation of research students with a profusion of available scholarships, thanks to our National Government, to imagine those dark dreary days of widespread depression and unemployment. In this period of depressing darkness this living embodiment of personal sacrifice—a Gautama Buddha in Indian Science, inspired our generation with capacity and strength to struggle through our scientific education and research. The remarkable feature was that he achieved this, most often not by words or personal contact but by the mere fact that this Scientist Sannyashi worked and lived in Science College right there amidst us. Like all great Acharyas of history, his most deeply moving lesson was he himself.

Acharya's personal contact in his modest residential apartment in the Science College building, was limited to just a few fortunates, who rendered him indispensable personal service in many ways. But somehow his spirit of dedication, self-sacrifice, patriotism and hard work overflowed well beyond the bounds of this charmed circle of select few; it cast a spell over all of us who worked in Science College. Though he was moderate in

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his views on politics, and shunned hot-brand ideas which might land him into jail (he was too old for that as he himself sometimes said), he never failed to guide the nation by his wisdom and sagacity, towards self-reliance to win freedom. His dictum is well remembered —“Science can wait but Swaraj cannot.” His autobiography appeared just in time which was a living embodiment of his message. Have we proved ourselves to his expectation? Was he a success in his preaching? The answer is a qualified yes, yes only to the extent the time was ripe. But that does in no way, dim the light he shed round.

I have heard it said that his philosophy, his preachings, his platform were not his but that of his time; the stage was set, time demanded a personality of his stature and Acharya merely filled the gap. Such a viewpoint completely ignores the multifaced manifold of the human mind in all its subtlety and complexity. The Acharya of course, was the product of his era, an era when the oppressed national soul of India was crying out for her salvation and as such we shall never see like him again as his age is gone and gone forever. But I put it before you from my little personal knowledge of him, that Acharya was much in advance of his time—a man with a heart of golden compassion, an eternal soul soaring above the mortal limits of his earthly bounds. One does not judge such souls by this grossly material standards, but one looks up to him to derive strength in their struggles; rational and irrational, we all did it. And, there lies Acharya's immortal greatness.

I might be pardoned if I would add one or two personal anecdotes about this great son of India. My mother was a devotee of Mahatma Gandhi, Congress and Swadeshi and she almost succeeded to brainwash me to believe in these things. When Sir P. C. Ray made emphatically the point, “Drinking tea, or drinking poison?” (चा पान ना विषपान), my mother immediately embraced this principle for the whole family, we all became strict teetotallers (my father was always a confirmed nonsmoker). We could not live in this paradise for long however. As soon as I had some personal contact with the Acharya, I noticed a number of tea cups in his room. I presumed these were for the entertainment of his guests, whom he received in profusion. My simple naivete got the first rude shock of my life, however, when I found Acharya enjoying tea regularly. One of us had the audacity to ask him about it. He felt somewhat uncomfortable. Now I know how impossible it is to get away from the clutches of habit-forming drugs even for a Scientist-Sannyashi.

Another personal episode, I crave your indulgence for mentioning, concerns a colloquium on colloid chemistry which was organized by the peerless indefatigable organizer, Prof. J. N. Mukherjee in the Calcutta Museum building in 1935. We were told that the Governor was likely to visit and all the students of Dr. Mukherjee including myself worked hard for the whole day to make all the exhibits and demonstrations, a success. A fairly strong earthquake during the day which ripped open the eastern side of the Museum Building (and devastated Muzzafarpur, we learnt later) could not damp our enthusiasm. By the evening we were all very hungry because neither we had the money nor the courage to get into any nearby restaurant as these were mostly visited by white-skinned people and their quislings. As a result when light refreshments and hard drinks were being served in course of the colloquium in the evening to the high ranking visitors, quite a few of us partook of the same avidly, mostly patties and vermouth, a word we heard for the first time in our life. Our hunger satiated, we staggered back home, in groups ready to render mutual help as someone jocosely cautioned us that vermouth might knock us down on the way.

Next day the report was duly given to the Acharya by a member of his selected circle that some students of Science College, particularly this poor self, imbibed heavily and had to be carried home from the Maidan by friends and police. Acharya was aflame at the news of this "moral degradation" of his science college brood. He wanted to catch and punish the culprits by his own already mentioned "patented" method. On getting scent of this we vanished for days and were particularly careful not to cross path with him for weeks. He punished a few minor culprits meanwhile but as usual he cooled down in no time and forgot completely all about it, and normal relations were restored.

Ladies and gentlemen, Acharya P. C. Ray had a vision of an India great in science and technology; he gave his life for it. On this birth day of his let us remember gratefully his honest service to the nation and let us pledge honestly to work to make his vision a reality.